

THE USE OF MODERN EDUCATIONAL PLATFORMS IN THE LEARNING PROCESS.

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Introduction. The modern education system is undergoing significant transformations driven by digital technologies and platforms. The introduction of digital platforms has not only changed how lessons are organized but also significantly impacted the relationships between teachers and students. During the pandemic, the necessity for remote learning surged, further highlighting the critical role of modern educational platforms. Today, platforms like Moodle, Google Classroom, and Edmodo provide teachers and students with a wide range of tools, offering advantages over traditional education methods. Using modern educational platforms makes the learning process more interactive and efficient. These platforms simplify lesson management and make it easier for students to grasp the material. Therefore, it is essential to study the development of these platforms and their impact on the educational process.

Keywords: Modern educational platforms, remote learning, digital education, online learning platforms, interactive learning.

Main part

1. The capabilities of modern educational platforms

Today's digital platforms offer teachers effective tools for organizing lessons and simplifying the learning process. Platforms like Moodle and Google Classroom not only allow teachers to upload educational materials but also provide tools for creating tests, managing assignments, and automating the assessment system [1].

For example, the **Moodle** platform enables continuous communication between teachers and students while tracking students' achievements and gaps. Through this platform, educational materials can be posted, and tests, assignments, and projects can be created for independent learning. Additionally, Moodle allows teachers to analyze student activity and adjust the learning process accordingly

[2].

Another popular platform, **Google Classroom**, simplifies lesson management and enhances collaboration between teachers and students. This platform helps students and teachers exchange information easily and ensures assignments are completed on time [3].

2. Interactive learning through modern educational platforms

Modern platforms allow for the integration of innovative teaching methods. **Interactive learning** encourages active participation from students, helping them develop independent thinking and problem-solving skills. For instance, platforms with virtual labs or simulations offer students the opportunity to learn practical applications in an online environment. These digital platforms merge practical and theoretical knowledge [4].

Platforms like **Edmodo** enable students to ask questions, engage in discussions, and receive immediate feedback from teachers. Additionally, these platforms automatically record all assignments and results, providing a clear overview of students' progress [5].

3. The impact of modern educational platforms on educational quality

Modern educational platforms play a crucial role in improving educational quality. Digital platforms provide teachers with real-time insights into students' learning progress. This allows teachers to identify factors that may be hindering students' learning and make necessary adjustments to the learning process. Additionally, these platforms promote independence in learning, encouraging students to take responsibility for their education [6].

The interactive functions of these platforms make the learning process more engaging, motivating students to participate actively in lessons. At the same time, the learning process can be personalized, with materials adapted to each student's needs [7].

Conclusion

Modern educational platforms have revolutionized the education system. They simplify the learning process, strengthen the interaction between teachers and students, and make lessons more interactive and effective. The use of such platforms in education highlights the benefits of digital tools and contributes to improving the quality of education. These technologies are expected to further develop, introducing new innovative approaches to the educational system.

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